

An Roinn Oideachais
Department of Education

Institiúid Oideachais
Institute of Education

Supporting the Literacy Development of Children with Additional Needs in Early Childhood Education in Ireland (From Birth to 7 Years)

A Review of the Literature

**Prepared by Sinéad McNally and Christina O’Keeffe, Institute of
Education, Dublin City University, for the Department of Education**

Author Note

Sinéad McNally <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9501-2535>

Christina O’Keeffe <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7028-2398>

Suggested Citation

McNally, S., & O’Keeffe, C. (2022a). *Supporting the literacy development of children with additional needs in early childhood education in Ireland (from birth to 7 years). A review of the literature*. Department of Education (Ireland).

Supporting the Literacy Development of Children with Additional Needs in Early Childhood Education in Ireland (from birth to 8 years)

Sinéad McNally and Christina O’Keeffe

Overview

This report shares key findings and recommendations from two systematic reviews of the research literature to identify best practice and supports for the development of early literacy skills for students with special educational needs in Early Childhood Education (ECE) (birth to 8). ECE in Ireland encompasses Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) settings (sometimes referred to as the Early Years’ sector in which children are educated and cared for from birth to age six) and in the infant classes in primary schools in Ireland (in which children are typically aged four to eight).

The first study, a systematic review of systematic reviews, yielded limited research from which to develop recommendations to inform practice in inclusive ECE so a second, full systematic review of the literature was undertaken. Though this also highlighted a dearth of empirical research on inclusive literacy practices in the past ten years, several recommendations can be made on the basis of this systematic review.

The report begins by stating the central research question and outlining the search strategy underpinning both systematic review studies. In the narrative report, we provide an introduction and overview of background research literature on literacy supports for children with additional needs in ECE in order to contextualise the findings from the systematic reviews. The report is then split in two sections: the first presents the themes, findings, summary and set of recommendations from the systematic review of systematic reviews; the second section presents the themes, findings, summary and set of recommendations from the systematic review of the research literature.

Research Question

1. How can young children with special educational needs be supported in developing literacy skills in ECEC settings and in the infant classes of primary schools in Ireland?

Key Search Terms for Literacy Skills in Early Special Education

Target Skills / Learning:

Literacy / emergent literacy / oral language

Additional Learning Needs:

Special education / inclusive education / developmental disability / intellectual disability /
Autism / Dyslexia / Down Syndrome

Setting/Context:

Early childhood education / intervention / instruction / preschool

Target Study:

Systematic review / meta-analysis / research synthesis

Search syntax with key words: ("literacy" OR "emergent literacy" OR "oral language" OR "verbal skills") AND ("intellectual disabilit*" OR "developmental disabilit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*" OR "special education" OR "inclusive education" OR "autis*" OR "early intervention*") AND ("systematic review" OR "meta-analysis" OR "research synthesis")

Key Data Sources Consulted

Literature in the systematic review was from 2011 onwards with some reference to earlier seminal works. The search string was entered in the following databases (with amendments where necessary to match database requirements): SCOPUS, EBSCO (Academic Complete Search, CINAHL, ERIC, Education Complete Search, Education Index, PsychInfo) and Web of Science. In addition to the systematic search of the above databases, extensive hand searches were conducted on the reference lists of the most relevant systematic reviews, and on Google Scholar to identify articles and handbooks that did not appear in a systematic review, including 'Grey literature' such as reports published by international and national organisations, for example the NCCA and the NCSE. A consistent search strategy was applied across databases. Boolean search strings were developed using keywords listed above. A-priori inclusion criteria were developed in a protocol through collaborative discussions among the reports' authors before commencing the search process to identify potentially relevant studies. Covidence software was used to facilitate both systematic reviews and both projects will be archived and available as metadata for these reports.

Tabulation of Results (please see appendix A)

Table 1. Data extraction from a systematic review of systematic reviews on literacy supports for children with additional needs in Education (with some focus on ECE)

Table 2. Data extraction from a systematic review of systematic reviews on literacy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education

Table 3. Data extraction from a systematic review of the literature on literacy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education

Narrative Report

Introduction

This report focuses on identifying evidence-based literacy supports in Early Childhood Education (ECE) for children with additional needs. Due to shifts in educational policy towards inclusive education (Education Act, 1998; IDEA, 1997; Griffin & Shevlin, 2011; MacGiolla Phádraig, 2007), children with a range of additional needs are increasingly taught in mainstream classrooms in Ireland. The 2004 Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs (EPSEN) Act states that it is the right of all children,

[...] to be educated in an inclusive environment with children who do not have such needs unless the nature of or degree of those needs of the child is such that to do so would be inconsistent with (a) the best interests of the child as determined in accordance with any assessment carried out under this Act, or (b) the effective provision of education for children with whom the child is to be educated. (EPSEN Act, 2004, Section 2)

In the Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) sector in Ireland, the Access and Inclusion Model (AIM) supports inclusive ECE for children with additional needs from birth to six (Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth, 2016). ECE in Ireland also includes the junior and senior infant classrooms, including special classes, in primary school which is under the direction of the Department of Education and Skills. The early childhood curriculum, *Aistear* (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2009), is a play-based curriculum of ECEC in Ireland and this curriculum is also incorporated into the infant classrooms in addition to the primary school curriculum, in particular the recent Primary Language Curriculum (DES, 2016).

Early Childhood Education and Literacy Development

Early childhood is recognised as an important period of development during which environmental influences are especially impactful. For example, environmental input during the rapid period of brain development from birth to three is crucial in establishing brain structures (Shonkoff & Philips, 2000)

and for acquiring language (Clark, 2009; Kuhl, 2000). Drawing on socio-constructivist (Vygotsky, 1962) and bio-ecological theories of development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979) there is a large research literature indicating the important influence of initial environments on children's development (Crockenberg & Leerkes, 2003; Krishnan, 2010; Williams, Murray, McCrory, & McNally, 2013).

The importance of early childhood environments on children's development and learning can be clearly seen in the development of literacy skills during preschool and early primary school, often referred to as the development of 'emergent literacy' (Whitehurst & Lonigan, 1998). Literacy is defined in the *National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy - Literacy and Numeracy for Learning and Life 2011-2020* as "the capacity to read, understand and critically appreciate various forms of communication including spoken language, printed text, broadcast media, and digital media." (2011, p.8). It is considered essential for academic success (Duncan et al., 2007) and reading skill in primary school is a strong predictor of later reading ability (Cunningham & Stanovich, 1997).

However, the antecedents of reading skills are established in the early childhood years (Altun, Erden & Snow, 2018) with a large body of evidence demonstrating that reading skills in primary school are predicted by literacy skills in preschool (e.g. Storch & Whitehurst, 2002; Ozernov-Palchik et al., 2017). Altun and colleagues (2018) provide an excellent overview of the way in which early literacy skills are thought to impact future literacy skills:

Scarborough (2001) examined the multifaceted nature of reading and how children acquire reading skills. Phonological awareness, letter knowledge, and sight recognition of familiar words are the antecedents of the word recognition process, whereas vocabulary, print concepts, background knowledge, and verbal reasoning are the antecedents of language comprehension (Scarborough, 2009). Thus, attention has been drawn to the importance of experiences that might promote language and literacy during the early childhood period. (Altun, Erden & Snow, 2018, p.1099)

Extensive research on the home literacy and preschool environments also points to the importance of literacy activities as early as infancy for oral language skills (Leech, McNally, Daly & Corriveau, In Press) as well as shared reading during early childhood (Dickinson et al., 2012; Hindman et al., 2014; Muhinyi & Rowe, 2019; Zucker et al., 2012), visits to the library (Hedemark & Lindberg, 2018; Rankin, 2016), and conversation and turn taking (Donnelly & Kidd, 2021) for vocabulary and comprehension development.

In ECE classrooms, features (both instructional and structural) of quality literacy environments in preschool classrooms are linked to literacy development (Guo, Justice, Kaderavek, & McGinty, 2012; Wasik & Bond, 2001). ECE literacy environments for special education are also posited to be important for the development of emergent literacy skills for children with additional needs, with research highlighting the importance of providing a wide range of types of books to all young children as well as rich print-related resources and enhancing teachers' instructional supports

through tailored professional development for teaching literacy for young children with additional needs (Guo et al., 2013).

Literacy Instruction for Children with Additional Needs in Early Childhood Education

While literacy is recognised as one of the most important life skills for all children given its importance for increased quality of life and to thrive in society across multiple contexts, there is a dearth of literature on effective literacy instruction for children with severe impairment and additional needs in mainstream classroom contexts (Toews & Kurth, 2019). The lack of research is especially stark in terms of rigorous research on effective literacy teaching practices for minimally verbal children in inclusive educational settings (Toews & Kurth, 2019, p. 136). Comprehensive literacy programmes for typically developing children aim to include a focus on five central components of reading instruction: phonics, phonemic awareness, fluency, vocabulary, and reading comprehension (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development, 2000). Similarly, the newly rolled out Primary Language Curriculum (2016) is an integrated model that incorporates language and literacy in the form of oral language, reading and writing in Irish and English, and within which there is an emphasis on the development of phonics, phonemic awareness, fluency, vocabulary and reading comprehension. However, historically, comprehensive literacy instruction which incorporates these components was not offered for children with severe needs as the emphasis was on mastery of pre-requisite skills such as phonemic awareness (Toews & Kurth, 2019). In their call to action for further research on literacy instruction in mainstream contexts for children with additional needs, Toews & Kurth (2019) highlight that children with significant intellectual disabilities often struggle with these pre-requisite skills and that the focus for these children has been on teaching functional literacy skills rather than providing a comprehensive literacy programme.

In a systematic review of research on the emergent literacy skills of preschool children with ASD, Westerveld and her colleagues (2016) give an excellent overview of emergent literacy skills (p.37) and highlight that children with ASD show more difficulties in reading comprehension (meaning-related skills) than in word recognition abilities (related to decoding). Emergent literacy skills which are the “skills, knowledge, and attitudes that are developmental precursors to reading and writing” (Whitehurst & Lonigan, 1998, p. 848), include both “*code*-related skills (such as letter knowledge, print concepts, early name writing, and early developing phonological awareness), as well as *meaning*-related skills, including vocabulary, grammatical ability, and story retelling and comprehension (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development [NICHD], 2005; Pullen & Justice, 2003)” (Westerveld et al., 2016, p. 37). They highlight that while children with ASD are at risk of reading difficulties (Nation, Clarke, Wright, & Williams, 2006), this is more so due to difficulties predominantly in *reading comprehension* rather than in word recognition (decoding) skills (Westerveld et al., 2016):

Learning to read is just one of many challenges faced by children with ASD, given the pervasive and multifaceted nature of the disorder. Yet, given that learning to read commences in the early developmental period and is inextricably linked to educational outcomes, there is a strong case for it being given greater priority in early intervention programs for children with ASD. (p. 46).

Calls for greater research on teaching literacy to children with additional needs in a mainstream school context are not new in the field of special education and have been highlighted for over a decade (e.g. Kliwer, 2008; Lewis & Norwich, 2005). This gap in research is even more critical with regards to emergent literacy for young children with additional needs. Therefore, in this report we extracted and synthesised data from included studies in the context of key areas of emergent literacy in particular: (1) recognizing environmental print, (2) understanding the form and function of print, (3) recognizing the relationship between speech and print, (4) phonological awareness, and (5) development of oral language (Dickinson & Snow, 1987; Notari-Syverson, O'Connor, & Vadasy, 1998, as listed by Botts et al., 2014). We further highlighted findings in the context of the type of additional need specified in each study as children with different disabilities or delays may have unique profiles in terms of learning challenges with regard to specific emergent literacy skills.

Study Aims: A Systematic Review of Literacy for Children with Additional Needs in ECE

We sought to identify and extract robust findings in the research literature on teaching literacy skills for young children with additional needs. First, we conducted a systematic review of systematic reviews. However, as described in section one of this report, this systematic search revealed no systematic review on literacy in the early years (from birth to seven years) for children with additional needs. By broadening our search, we were able to include **three** systematic reviews (Boyle et al., 2019; Khowaja & Salim, 2013; Wanzek et al., 2018) in which at least 50% of the included studies had an early childhood focus. Twenty-eight systematic reviews (included in table 1 in appendix 1) were identified which included a broad age range of participants but from which it was not possible to identify findings specific to younger pupils. Given the qualitative differences in teaching contexts in early childhood education and older primary school classrooms, these systematic reviews were excluded as they did not analyse or synthesise research by children's ages and classroom context, and thus did not allow for identification of instructional approaches appropriate for ECE.

Second, as we found no systematic review which focused on literacy instruction for children with additional needs in early childhood education, we undertook a systematic review of the literature and report the data extraction, narrative synthesis and recommendations in the second half of this report. This two-pronged approach was adopted (i.e. both a systematic review of systematic reviews and a full systematic review of the literature) to ensure that relevant research literature was identified

from which we could make meaningful, evidence-based recommendations for literacy instruction for young pupils with additional needs.

A Note on Methodology

The search syntax was constructed such that systematic reviews and original research studies on (a) literacy instruction for young children with (b) additional needs in (c) early childhood education could be identified. With regards to the first sphere / focus of the search syntax, a broad definition of literacy was used, drawing on the definitions cited earlier. For the second sphere or focus of the search syntax, a broad and inclusive approach to ‘additional needs’ was used and included all children with an identifiable impairment, disability or delay. Studies were included only where children had been formally diagnosed or assessed. Therefore, for the purposes of this report, potentially vague terms such as ‘struggling readers’ or ‘at-risk readers’ (especially where this may be due to EAL or low SES) were excluded. Studies which focused on literacy instruction for young children with EAL were excluded from both systematic reviews unless the children also had a significant impairment or disability. This was done primarily because the literature on children with EAL indicates many ways in which the curriculum can be adapted to support bi/multilingual development (Demie & Lewis, 2018; Harris & Ó Duibhir, 2011; Liu et al., 2017; Oxley & de Cat, 2021). Further, growing up bilingual/multilingual can, with adaptations to curriculum and instruction, contribute positively to children’s emergent literacy (references). As such the types of supports identified for children with disabilities were considered qualitatively different in aim and scope. Finally, the third sphere or focus of the search syntax, Early Years or ECE was defined as education from birth to seven years (the age at which almost all children in Ireland have completed senior infants).

Finally, in this report, we did not assess the risk of publication bias or include a quality appraisal of studies in the systematic review of the literature due to the heterogeneity of studies. However, we have provided, within the space constraints of table 2, detail on studies to allow readers to gauge the quality of study design, appropriateness of sampling, and types of findings reported in light of targeted outcomes. Together these give an indication of the quality of the research in included studies without conducting a full quality appraisal.

1. A Systematic Review of Systematic Reviews of Literacy Supports for Children with Additional Needs in Early Childhood Education

Key Themes and Findings

Overall, three systematic review studies were included for data extraction (Boyle et al., 2019; Khowaja & Salim, 2013; Wanzek et al., 2018), details of which will be outlined below in relation to sample

demographics and instructional approaches. Findings are described according to a three-point classification system: positive, mixed or negative given that the diversity of study designs has meant that it is difficult to compare study results (Gunning et al., 2019; Tupou et al., 2019; Verschuur et al., 2014). Single-case experimental design studies were classified as positive if all participants demonstrated an increase across all literacy outcomes, mixed if only some participants increased performance across literacy outcomes and negative if no participant demonstrated an increase in any literacy outcomes. Findings from group designs were classified as positive if statistically significant results were reported across all literacy outcomes, mixed if statistically significant results were reported across some but not all literacy outcomes and negative if no statistically significant results were reported across any literacy outcomes.

Additional Needs of Study Participants

From the systematic review of systematic reviews, we see that two of the three studies (Boyle et al., 2019; Khowaja & Salim, 2013) that met the inclusion criteria focused on literacy skills for children with ASD (the third study focused on learning disabilities which is a distinct group of pupils). In our systematic review of research literature which focused exclusively on literacy supports for children with additional needs in the early years, we found a similar focus on ASD in six of the 15 studies (discussed separately due to the original studies reviewed).

Second to language impairments, ASD is the most common disability in special education in Ireland (National Council for Special Education 2016; 2017), affecting approximately one in 68 children (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, 2014). It is characterized by impairments in social-communication skills, and repetitive or restricted behaviours and interests (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). ASD is a spectrum disorder due to the large heterogeneity in severity of symptoms, and difficulties in language skills often co-occur as well as intellectual disability (Williams, Botting, & Boucher, 2008) (for a succinct overview of language and cognitive impairments in ASD, see Westerveld et al., 2016 (p.38)).

As each study does not have a similar sample of participants in terms of additional needs or in terms of target literacy skills, the themes and findings are reported for each of the three studies here. Although all of the systematic reviews included sample participants in which a minimum of 50% of children were aged 0-8 years, none of the systematic reviews focused exclusively on the Early Years or Early Childhood Education (see table 1 for the list of studies which were excluded due to reporting mixed age cohorts including some below the age of 8).

Instructional Approaches

Each systematic review focuses on a different aspect of early literacy instruction, including shared reading, intensive reading instruction and the use of computer-based instruction, all of which will be described in detail in the following section in relation to targeted sample/population.

Shared Reading for Children with ASD

Boyle and colleagues' (2019) systematic review showed a range of effect sizes for shared reading depending on the outcome measured, with the largest effect sizes reported for listening comprehension and the smallest effect sizes for measures of expressive communication. Given the wide age range of participants in the studies reviewed by Boyle and her colleagues, there is tentative support here for shared reading for young children with ASD to support children's listening comprehension, communicative (e.g. answering questions, providing repeated storyline and initiations) and non-communicative acts (e.g. opening and turning pages of text, directing eye gaze to text or participants) and for the development of expressive communication. Positive outcomes were found even where components of the shared reading interaction varied across studies, suggesting shared reading is a particularly robust intervention as part of literacy supports for young children with ASD.

Computer-Based Instruction for children with ASD

Khowaja and Salim (2013) found frequent use of multimedia methods (e.g. graphic representations, audio and hypertext) and explicit instruction (in relation to vocabulary definitions or related attributes) to teach vocabulary to young children with ASD, and 'question answering' (whereby children answered question posed by instructor after which they received feedback) was a method commonly used to teach text comprehension. There was large support across five of the 11 studies reviewed for the use of Computer-Based Instruction (CBI) to teach reading comprehension in particular in the development of interactive and engaging learning environments, though the authors caution that several studies did not report any positive effects which may be due to the heterogeneity of ASD. This is notable given the increasing support regarding the use of computer-based interventions in supporting learners with ASD in the classroom within the wider literature (Grynszpan et al., 2014; Pennington, 2010; Petrovska & Trajkovski, 2019; Ramdoss et al., 2012) as well as support for digital literacy techniques within the newly developed Primary Language Curriculum (NCCA, 2016).

Support for Early Intensive Reading Interventions for Learning Disabilities

Wanzek and colleagues (2018) found small positive gains in reading performance for children, with learning disabilities and those at risk from learning disabilities, from kindergarten to grade three after intensive interventions (classified as 100 sessions or more). Limited variability was reported in the effect sizes across studies, suggesting that intervention commonalities were driving positive effects and these commonalities were (a) a high level of standardization (b) instructional content addressed

phonological awareness, phonics and word recognition and fluency and (c) school staff or community members implemented the interventions. We will come back to the importance of the role of the interventionist and the contribution of educators to delivery of the literacy interventions in the systematic review of the literature.

Summary

Overall, what is most striking about this research literature is the absence of a focus on literacy supports in the *early years* for children with a range of additional needs. That is to say that we struggled to find systematic reviews which targeted emergent literacy or literacy skill development in the critical early childhood period. The three studies covered important topics in the literacy research literature, including a wide range of important skills such as vocabulary, reading comprehension and phonological awareness. However, given that none focused exclusively on ECE instruction it is difficult to generalise to teaching young children with additional needs. Given that literacy skills develop in early childhood, and that this is a critical time for literacy development, this is a large gap in the systematic review literature which needs to be addressed. From three studies, we were able to glean support for some interventions and instructional practices for a small cohort of children with additional needs, namely, children with ASD and children broadly defined as learning disabled and at-risk of reading difficulties. Shared reading was strongly evidenced as an instructional approach that would support children with ASD's literacy skills in terms of listening comprehension, expressive communication and a range of communicative and non-communicative acts, including participation. Given the large body of evidence in the research literature on the importance of shared reading for children's early oral language (Leech, McNally, Daly & Corriveau, In Press; McNally, McCrory, Quigley & Murray, 2019) and literacy development (Dickinson et al., 2012; Hindman et al., 2014; Muhinyi & Rowe, 2019; Zucker et al., 2012) this is an especially promising intervention and one that already occurs in mainstream classrooms. Extending and adapting shared reading practices to target the literacy skills of young autistic children in preschool and infant primary school classrooms may be an effective and inclusive strategy for comprehension, expression and participation.

For a less well defined group of children with learning disabilities and at risk for learning disabilities, Wanzek et al. (2018) highlight the importance of intensive early interventions that target phonological awareness, phonics and word recognition and fluency. The fact that interventions were highly standardised and delivered in class by educators and school staff, emphasises the importance of evidence on interventions delivered by educators. The targeted skills in the interventions reviewed are important for decoding and for fluency and are well established as important early skills for typically developing children in early childhood and Wanzek's study indicates support for targeting these skills in children with additional needs (though with the caveat that the learning disabilities and at risk for reading disabilities were quite a broad group of additional needs).

Recommendations

On the basis of this systematic review of systematic reviews, we make five key recommendations:

1. Shared reading practices are an important instructional feature of inclusive preschool and primary school classrooms and there is a growing literature to support shared reading as a literacy support for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education (pillar 5).
2. Computer-Based Interventions (CBI) may support the development of reading comprehension for young autistic children (pillar 5) through the creation of interactive and engaging learning environments.
3. Early intensive reading interventions that focus on decoding skills, word recognition and fluency are likely to have a positive influence on literacy skills for children at-risk of reading difficulties. (pillar 5)
4. A systematic review of the research literature on ECE literacy instruction for children with a range of additional needs and disabilities needs to be undertaken and to be regularly updated with regard to research evidence. There are significant differences in the learning contexts for children across the educational lifespan and a clear gap in the literature synthesising findings on supporting the **early** literacy development of children with additional needs in educational contexts.
5. A systematic review of the literature on supporting early literacy skills for children with ASD is also needed given the extensive heterogeneity in language and cognitive skills of young autistic children. Young children with ASD are more likely than their neurotypical peers to experience reading difficulties: a regularly updated synthesis of best practice for supporting literacy for young autistic children in ECE is therefore essential.

2. A Systematic Review of the Literature on Literacy Supports for Children with Additional Needs in Early Childhood Education

Themes and Findings:

Overall, 15 studies met inclusion criteria and were included for data extraction, details of which will be outlined below in relation to sample demographics and instructional approaches. Once again, findings are described according to a three-point classification system: positive, mixed or negative (see previous section). Themes and key findings based on the data extraction presented in table 3 are reported in narrative form here. Recommendations from narrative synthesis are highlighted following a short summary of the findings.

Study Characteristics

Additional Needs of Participants

Language impairments and Autism Spectrum Disorder were the two most commonly targeted additional needs in terms of literacy intervention in the included studies. This is in line with reported prevalence rates within Irish schools (NCSE, 2016; 2017). Across all studies, participants ranged from 2.92-6.10 years, with a reported mean age of 4.48 years. Participants were predominantly boys (with the exception of Justice and colleagues' 2015 large-scale study).

Instructional Approaches

Studies targeted a wide range of instructional approaches including: reading interventions and literacy outcomes such as reading, decoding skills, fluency, print knowledge, digital literacy techniques, all of which will be described in detail in the following section in relation to targeted sample or population. It is also important to note that interventions drew on a range of methodologies including a large proportion of behavioural strategies which were developed from the extensive Early Intensive Behavioural Intervention literature (Benedek-Wood et al., 2016; Botts et al., 2014; Boyle et al., 2021; Lorah & Parnell, 2014; Quinn et al., 2020; Rahn et al., 2016; Towson et al., 2016; Wilcox et al., 2011). These included traditional behavioural components such as adult modelling (Benedek-Wood et al., 2016; Quinn et al., 2020; Rahn et al., 2016; Wilcox et al., 2011), imitation (Rahn et al., 2016; Towson et al., 2016), prompting (Botts et al., 2014; Boyle et al., 2021; Lorah & Parnell, 2014; Towson et al., 2016; Wilcox et al., 2011), time delay (Boyle et al., 2021; Towson et al., 2016), positive reinforcement (Benedek-Wood et al. 2016; Quinn et al., 2020; Rahn et al., 2016), expansions and recasts (Quinn et al., 2020; Rahn et al., 2016; Towson et al., 2016; Wilcox et al., 2011), commands and directives (Quinn et al., 2020 Rahn et al., 2016) as well as a combination of naturalistic behavioural approaches including individualised strategies and supports (Botts et al., 2014), use of interests and preferences (Botts et al., 2014; Rahn et al., 2016) and use of logically occurring antecedents and consequences (Botts et al., 2014; Rahn et al., 2016).

In just five of the 15 studies, the teacher implemented the intervention with over half the interventions implemented by the researcher. This is important to note when assessing the potential for generalising effectiveness of these instructional techniques to ECE settings and classrooms. Despite calls for collaboration between parents or caregivers and schools in supporting early literacy development (NCCA, 2016; NEPS, 2020), just one study (Justice et al., 2015) involved a dual implementation or collaborative approach between early childhood special educators and parents/caregivers. Justice and her colleagues examined differences in print knowledge outcomes

between children with language impairments receiving print-focused read-alouds as part of a home and school support condition and those exclusively receiving school support. Although no significant differences were reported between conditions, researchers attributed this to poor parent/caregiver fidelity and implementation. Two other studies (Colozzo et al., 2016; Pears et al., 2016) incorporated home/school practice sessions as part of interventions: however, Pears and colleagues did not assess the effectiveness of these and ran parent groups for awareness in addition to the researcher implemented pre-K summer program; Colozzo and colleagues used parent or school input supplementary to researcher implemented intervention with no clear pattern emerging in terms of impact and problems surrounding implementation.

Location, Context and Implementation

All 15 studies which met the inclusion criteria for this systematic review were conducted in North America, with 14 of the 15 studies conducted in the USA. The majority of studies were implemented within preschool settings (n=10) or pre-kindergarten (N=2) settings with two studies conducted in research centres. Most of these settings (n=7) involved inclusive classrooms, comprising of children with disabilities and typically developing peers with two studies focusing on special classrooms for children with disabilities. Although 12 of the 14 eligible studies were conducted within school settings, just three were implemented as part of classroom activities with four others conducted in isolated or quiet areas and unspecified across five studies. This is of particular importance given the drive for inclusive class supports (Finkelstein et al., 2019; Florian, 2015; Lindner & Schwab, 2020; Lingo et al., 2011; Molbaek, 2017).

Frequency of interventions ranged from twice daily to once weekly, with the majority of interventions implemented two times weekly. The intensity of interventions ranged from 5 to 180 minutes with average 40 minutes and finally, the duration of sessions lasted from 2 weeks to 45 weeks with an average of 17 weeks.

The majority of interventions focused on individualised/1-1 sessions (N=6) with five studies conducted as part of groups 2-5 (children with disabilities and typically developing peers) and three implemented as part of whole-class. Given the focus on inclusive class supports, this is of particular importance when considering feasible interventions in classroom contexts.

Given the dearth of early childhood literacy research for children with additional needs, we imposed no restrictions in the inclusion criteria regarding research design except for single case study designs which were excluded due to the lack of generalisability of findings. As can be seen in table 3, a wide range of research designs were used including RCTs (N=3), single-subject experimental designs (N=12) and a survey design (N=1).

Support for Reading Interventions in Special Early Childhood Education

Several studies reported findings on reading-specific interventions, including interventions on shared reading (Boyle et al., 2021), dialogic book reading (e.g. Towson et al., 2016) and print-focussed reading (Justice et al., 2015). Overall 8 of the 15 studies included some form of shared / dialogic reading intervention and several of these included reading in a digital format.

The majority of intervention studies reported positive findings for young children though target literacy skills differed across intervention type and for target group of young pupils. For example, Justice and her colleagues (2015) investigated the impact of a print-focussed intervention on print knowledge compared to regular reading of books in early childhood special classrooms. Print knowledge was assessed using a composite index of three constructs: 1) Print concept knowledge (preschool word and print awareness); 2) Alphabet knowledge (Subtests of Phonological Awareness and Literacy Screening Pre-K); 3) Name writing (Name Writing Subtest of PALS Pre-K). Using a large sample of children with Language Impairment, they found a positive impact of the print-focused intervention though this was moderated by nonverbal cognition. Boyle and her colleagues (2021) investigated the use of shared e-book reading with dynamic text and speech output on children with disabilities' single-word reading skills and found positive effects of the intervention. Shared reading was also a component of Colozzo and colleagues' (2016) intervention study which found positive effects of a hybrid reading intervention on phonological awareness for children with a range of disabilities, primarily Down Syndrome: letter identification, sound identification, concepts of print, sight words. Mandak et al. (2019) studied the effects of a digital reading support on sight word recognition by three children with ASD and found the Dynamic Text and Speech Output Tablet Software effective in increasing sight word reading.

Two studies (Rahn et al., 2016; Towson et al., 2016) investigated dialogic reading though in different ways and for different populations and both reported mixed findings with regard to the impact on young children's target vocabulary skills. Towson et al. (2016) investigated the inclusion of pause time in dialogic reading for children with significant developmental delay and found a significant increase on near-transfer expressive and receptive vocabulary tests across both targeted and untargeted vocabulary and no significant differences across remaining measures of receptive and expressive vocabulary, although positive trends were reported in intervention dialogic reading group. No significant difference in pre-literacy skills was reported although positive trends were reported in intervention group. The authors concluded that children with significant needs may not be able to generalize newly learned words as quickly (i.e. they need greater time and intensity of intervention) than typically developing children (Towson et al., 2016).

Rahn and colleagues (2016) compared vocabulary learning in activity-based learning (a naturalistic play-based intervention with embedded learning opportunities for learning on a range of outcomes including vocabulary) and a dialogic shared book reading intervention and found effectiveness on increasing target vocabulary for both interventions for three children with developmental delays in pre-kindergarten. This was the only study to evaluate the impact of play-based interventions on literacy outcomes of children with disabilities which is surprising given the emphasis on playful approaches and learning opportunities within the Primary Language Curriculum (NCCA, 2016) and more broadly within the literature on early childhood language and literacy instruction (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2009; Lillard et al., 2013; Weisberg et al., 2013).

Piasta et al.'s 2020 study on the Read It Again (RIA) programme is the only study in the systematic review to report no significant effects of an intervention on the target outcomes. This was a largescale randomised controlled trial study comparing regular shared reading to RIA. RIA however did increase teachers' print knowledge, phonological awareness, narrative, and vocabulary instruction during shared book reading; and though teachers' instruction did not predict children's outcomes, a small indirect effect was reported on a composite of children's code-based skills, in which RIA meaning-focused instruction affected code-based skills. Quinn and colleagues, also 2020, reported mixed findings on the use of aided, augmentative and alternative communication (AAAC) in small group dialogic reading. What is unique about this study in our review is that the intervention focused on young children with Down Syndrome and the mixed results reported in table 3 highlight the importance of child-level characteristics in the impact of the intervention on outcomes.

Research Support for Teaching Decoding Skills (Phonological and Phonemic Awareness)

Historically teaching decoding skills to children with limited speech was considered problematic. Thirty percent of children with ASD will not develop speech skills and will find it difficult to take part in reading instruction which requires spoken responses (Benedek et al) and for this reason the focus has been on sight-word reading. In order to develop a more comprehensive literacy programme for children with ASD in preschool who have limited speech Benedek et al investigated the effectiveness and social validity of literacy activities in learning Letter-Sound Correspondences (LSC) by young children with ASD and limited speech. LSC is a decoding skill critical for learning to read and write words. They found modified and adapted LSC instruction was effective, efficient and considered socially valid by Early Childhood Special Educators. Though several limitations with regard to external validity and ability to extend findings to larger population have been identified with single-subject experimental design (Janosky, 2005; Kratochwill et al., 2010), the findings are promising as they extend the literature on teaching LSC to autistic children with limited speech pre-primary school in the EYs.

Botts and colleagues (2014) also targeted decoding skills including phonological awareness and found that highly structured direct instruction was more effective than activity-based instruction and possibly led to greater effectiveness and efficiency through “[...] more rapid learning when compared with other strategies and that stable learning takes place in an environment of individualized, systematic, and explicit teaching (Engelmann, 1980; Gersten, Carnine, & Woodward, 1987; Gersten et al., 1986; Rosenshine, 1976; Wolery et al., 1992)” (Botts et al., 2014, p.131).

Colozzo et al. (2016) adapted a hybrid approach involving whole-word (visual) and analytic (phonics) based reading strategies for children with Down Syndrome. Following shared book reading and instructional activities, all students reported improvements across all literacy measures including phonological awareness, letter identification, sound identification, print concepts and sight words. In addition, positive findings were reported across some participants in relation to expressive language skills. Thus, authors highlight the potential of expanding beyond phonics based instruction and decoding skills to sight word acquisition for children with Down Syndrome, given heterogeneous profiles.

Travers et al. (2011) compared traditional teacher-led group instruction involving alphabetic books and computer-assisted instruction on the alphabet recognition skills of children with ASD within special classrooms. Authors discuss the importance of examining decoding practices for children with ASD within the classroom, which can often be overlooked in preference of behavioural outcomes. Results reported positive findings across both interventions with reported benefits attributed to behavioural practices including modelling, prompting, shaping as well as the incorporation of interesting and motivating materials throughout both interventions.

Research Support for the Use of Digital Formats and Technology to Teach Literacy Skills

Four of the included studies employed digital instructional methods to increase literacy skills, ranging from sight word acquisition (Mandak et al., 2019), single word reading skills (Boyle et al., 2021), alphabet recognition skills (Travers et al., 2011) and letter writing acquisition (Lorah & Parnell, 2014). For example, Boyle et al. (2021) demonstrated the positive impact of a shared e-book reading intervention with dynamic text and speech output based on tablet on the single word reading skills across six children with developmental disabilities. Lorah and Parnell (2014) also examined the impact of digital instructional strategies on three children with developmental disabilities. This involved the use of an iPod touch ‘letter school’ application on letter writing acquisition, which demonstrated positive effects across two out of three participants. The remaining two studies examined the impact of digital formats on children with ASD. Firstly, Mandak et al. (2019) reported the positive impact of dynamic text and speech output based on tablet software on the sight word acquisition of three children with ASD. Travers et al. (2011) also examined the impact of computer

assisted instruction on the alphabet recognition skills of 17 children with ASD. This was in comparison to a traditional teacher-led instruction. Results reported positive effects across both interventions which the authors attributed to the incorporation of well-established behavioural strategies. These studies provide some evidence in support of the use of digital literacy methods as proposed in the Primary Language Curriculum (NCCA, 2016) which includes a focus on electronic and digital texts, and multi-media approaches.

Teacher Self-Efficacy as Important for Teaching Literacy Skills in Early Special Education

One of the 15 included studies examined 73 early childhood special educators' self-efficacy in relation to children with disabilities and typically developing peers as well as relations between child specific self-efficacy and print knowledge literacy outcomes (letter identification, print and word awareness, name writing). Results revealed that early childhood special education teachers demonstrated less self-reported self-efficacy for children with disabilities in comparison to typically developing peers, with teachers reporting the lowest level of self-efficacy for children with ASD (Guo et al., 2021). In addition, teachers' child specific self-efficacy was associated with print knowledge for both children with disabilities and typically developing peers. Therefore, teacher self-efficacy is regarded as an important predictor as part of outcomes in inclusive early childhood classroom.

Summary

Extracting and synthesising data from the 15 studies in this systematic review in the context of emergent literacy skills (recognising environmental print, understanding the form and function of print, recognising the relationship between speech and print, phonological awareness, and the development of oral language), we see clear themes and gaps emerging. The range of studies varied widely in the types of additional needs of participating children, instructional technologies used, emergent literacy skills targeted, type of interventionist (educator or researcher), and study design (from single-subject to RCT). To draw out themes we focused on both the type of intervention and the literacy skills targeted to identify commonalities for children with additional needs in the early years.

In terms of commonly used and effective interventions, shared reading (implemented as dialogic reading or read alouds or shared e-books) was the most frequently implemented intervention out of the 15 studies with positive effects reported generally for children's literacy skills. Three larger programmes (KITS, TELL and a school readiness programme) were also evaluated with positive outcomes on a range of early literacy skills. Digital formats for instruction were part of four studies which reported positive findings (Boyle et al., 2021; Lorah & Parnell, 2014; Mandak et al., 2019; Travers et al., 2011) though all with different target literacy outcomes and different types of intervention. Findings indicate positive support for digital formats and the use of technology (AAC in

Quinn et al.'s 2020 study of DS) with Lorah and Parnell (2014) showing some preference for digital formats for 2 young children with developmental disabilities.

With regard to the literacy skills targeted, two studies specifically targeted decoding skills (Benedek-Wood et al., 2016; Botts et al., 2014) in order to contribute to the growing literature on how to build a comprehensive literacy programme for children with additional needs in ECE. Two studies focused on sight word recognition (Boyle et al., 2021; Mandak et al., 2019) and two studies focused on vocabulary acquisition (Rahn et al., 2016; Towson et al., 2016). Only one study focused on the literacy skill of print knowledge (Justice et al.'s 2015 read aloud study) and one on writing (Lorah & Parnell, 2014).

This systematic review highlights the limited literature on ECE instruction for children with additional needs. In particular, it highlights the need to consider the type of additional need in reviewing the evidence of support for instructional strategies. Literature included here shows support for well-established instructional strategies (shared reading for example) as well as the feasibility of teaching decoding skills to children previously considered unable to learn these pre-requisite skills for later literacy development. However, in such a small number of studies spanning a several types of disabilities and research designs, no one instructional strategy has sufficient evidence from which to make clear recommendations except to highlight evidence in support of comprehensive literacy programmes for children with additional needs, including children with limited speech. The use of technology and digital formats for instruction also came out as a theme in this review.

Finally, we included a study on teacher self-efficacy as the outcomes assessed related to children's early literacy skills. The findings here are notable and important for educators in the EY. Self-efficacy is critical in supporting young children with additional needs' literacy skills. However, while we recommend a clear focus on teacher self-efficacy, our systematic review highlights that much more research and synthesis of research on teaching literacy skills for children *specific to their additional needs* is required to inform professional development such that teacher self-efficacy can be enhanced.

Recommendations

1. Shared reading which is an established practice in early childhood classrooms has a growing research evidence base as a positive strategy for teaching emergent literacy skills to young children with additional needs. As a common practice in ECE it is a good context for targeting specific skills. (pillar 5)

2. Dialogic reading, a form of shared reading, may be especially helpful in building vocabulary skills (oral language) for children with additional needs as highlighted in two studies in this review. (pillar 5).
3. Phonological awareness and decoding skills should be included as target skills for children with additional needs though the research base on this is still emerging. It is important to aim for the development of comprehensive literacy interventions and programmes for children with additional needs though the research literature is still developing in this area. (pillar 5)
4. Teacher self-efficacy is important in teaching literacy skills to young children with additional needs. As such CPD which focuses on enhancing knowledge, skills and self-efficacy will be important for teaching literacy skills in inclusive ECE (pillar 5)
5. Increased awareness should be given to quality of the literacy environment in ECE more widely and also specifically for special education in the Early Years – this is based on an extensive and detailed study by Justice in the USA which highlighted low to moderate quality of the early literacy environment in terms of structural and instructional features (pillar 5)
6. Involving parents is an important component in inclusive literacy strategies and fits with a bio-ecological and child-centred view of young children in special education.
7. The research on play-based literacy instruction is limited and given the importance of play pedagogies in ECE this is a gap which needs to be addressed in the research literature and in practice.

References

*Study included in the review

Afacan, K., Wilkerson, K. L., & Ruppard, A. L. (2018). Multicomponent reading interventions for students with intellectual disability. *Remedial and Special Education, 39*(4), 229-242. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0741932517702444>

Alnahdi, G. H. (2015). Teaching Reading for Students with Intellectual Disabilities: A Systematic Review. *International Education Studies, 8*(9), 79-87.

Altun, D., Tantekin Erden, F., & Snow, C. E. (2018). A multilevel analysis of home and classroom literacy environments in relation to preschoolers' early literacy development. *Psychology in the Schools, 55*(9), 1098-1120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22153>

Alquraini, T. A., & Rao, S. M. (2020). Developing and sustaining readers with intellectual and multiple disabilities: A systematic review of literature. *International Journal of Developmental Disabilities, 66*(2), 91-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20473869.2018.1489994>

American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders; DSM-V (5th ed.)*. American Psychiatric Association.

Bailey, B., & Arciuli, J. (2020). Reading instruction for children with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review and quality analysis. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders, 7*(2), 127-150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-019-00185-8>

- *Benedek-Wood, E., McNaughton, D., & Light, J. (2016). Instruction in letter-sound correspondences for children with autism and limited speech. *Topics in Early Childhood Special Education, 36*(1), 43-54. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0271121415593497>
- * Botts, D. C., Losardo, A. S., Tillery, C. Y., & Werts, M. G. (2014). A comparison of activity-based intervention and embedded direct instruction when teaching emergent literacy skills. *The Journal of Special Education, 48*(2), 120-134. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022466912449652>
- *Boyle, S. A., McNaughton, D., & Chapin, S. E. (2019). Effects of shared reading on the early language and literacy skills of children with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities, 34*(4), 205-214.
- *Boyle, S., McNaughton, D., Light, J., Babb, S., & Chapin, S. E. (2021). The Effects of Shared e-Book Reading With Dynamic Text and Speech Output on the Single-Word Reading Skills of Young Children with Developmental Disabilities. *Language, speech, and hearing services in schools, 52*(1), 426-435. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_LSHSS-20-00009
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2014). *Facts about ASD*. <http://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/facts.html>. Accessed 30 August 2021
- Clark, E.V. (2009). *First Language Acquisition*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511806698>
- *Colozzo, P., McKeil, L., Petersen, J. M., & Szabo, A. (2016). An early literacy program for young children with down syndrome: changes observed over one year. *Journal of policy and practice in intellectual disabilities, 13*(2), 102-110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jppi.12160>
- Crockenberg, S. & Leerkes, E. (2003). Infant negative emotionality, caregiving and family relationships. In A.C. Crouter & A. Booth (Eds), *Children's influence on family dynamics The negative side of relationships* (pp.57-78). New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers
- Cunningham, A. E., & Stanovich, K. E. (1997). Early reading acquisition and its relation to reading experience and ability 10 years later. *Developmental psychology, 33*(6), 934.
- Dessemontet, R. S., Martinet, C., de Chambrier, A. F., Martini-Willemin, B. M., & Audrin, C. (2019). A meta-analysis on the effectiveness of phonics instruction for teaching decoding skills to students with intellectual disability. *Educational Research Review, 26*, 52-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.01.001>
- Datchuk, S. M., & Kubina, R. M. (2013). A review of teaching sentence-level writing skills to students with writing difficulties and learning disabilities. *Remedial and Special Education, 34*(3), 180-192. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0741932512448254>
- Datchuk, S. M., Wagner, K., & Hier, B. O. (2020). Level and trend of writing sequences: A review and meta-analysis of writing interventions for students with disabilities. *Exceptional Children, 86*(2), 174-192. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0014402919873311>
- Demie, F., & Lewis, K. (2018). Raising achievement of English as additional language pupils in schools: implications for policy and practice. *Educational Review, 70*(4), 427-446. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2017.1344190>

- Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth (2016). *Access and Inclusion Model*. Dublin 2: The Stationery Office <https://aim.gov.ie/app/uploads/2016/06/AIM-Policy.pdf> Accessed 30 August 2021
- Department of Education and Skills (2017). *National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy - Literacy and Numeracy for Learning and Life 2011-2020*. Dublin 2: The Stationery Office https://www.education.ie/en/publications/education-reports/pub_ed_interim_review_literacy_numeracy_2011_2020.pdf Accessed 30 August 2021
- Department of Education and Skills (2016). *Primary Language Curriculum*. Dublin 2: The Stationery Office. https://curriculumonline.ie/getmedia/2a6e5f79-6f29-4d68-b850-379510805656/PLC-Document_English.pdf Accessed 30 August 2021
- Department of Education USA (2006). Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act Regulations. <https://sites.ed.gov/idea/> Accessed 30 August 2021
- Dickinson, D. K., Griffith, J. A., Golinkoff, R. M., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2012). How reading books fosters language development around the world. *Child Development Research*, 2012, 1-15.
- Donnelly, S., & Kidd, E. (2021). The Longitudinal Relationship Between Conversational Turn-Taking and Vocabulary Growth in Early Language Development. *Child Development*, 92(2), 609-625. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13511>
- Duncan, G. J., Dowsett, C. J., Claessens, A., Magnuson, K., Huston, A. C., Klebanov, P., ... & Japel, C. (2007). School readiness and later achievement. *Developmental psychology*, 43(6), 1428-1446. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0012-1649.43.6.1428>
- El Zein, F., Solis, M., Vaughn, S., & McCulley, L. (2014). Reading comprehension interventions for students with autism spectrum disorders: A synthesis of research. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 44(6), 1303-1322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-013-1989-2>
- Finkelstein, S., Sharma, U., & Furlonger, B. (2021). The inclusive practices of classroom teachers: a scoping review and thematic analysis. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(6), 735-762. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1572232>
- Finnegan, E., & Mazin, A. L. (2016). Strategies for increasing reading comprehension skills in students with autism spectrum disorder: A review of the literature. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 39(2), 187-219. <http://doi.org/10.1353/etc.2016.0007>
- Florian, L. (2015). "Conceptualising Inclusive Pedagogy: The Inclusive Pedagogical Approach in Action", *Inclusive Pedagogy Across the Curriculum (International Perspectives on Inclusive Education, Vol. 7)*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Bingley, pp. 11-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-363620150000007001>
- Gillespie, A., & Graham, S. (2014). A meta-analysis of writing interventions for students with learning disabilities. *Exceptional children*, 80(4), 454-473. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0014402914527238>
- Government of Ireland (1998). *The Education Act*. Dublin 2: The Stationery Office
- Government of Ireland (2004). *Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act*. Dublin 2: The Stationery Office
- Griffin, S., & Shevlin, M. (2011). *Responding to special educational needs: An Irish perspective*. Dublin: Gill Education

- Gunning, C., Breathnach, Ó, Holloway, J., McTiernan, A., & Malone, B. (2019). A systematic review of peer-mediated interventions for preschool children with autism spectrum disorder in inclusive settings. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 6 (1), 40-62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-018-0153-5>
- *Guo, Y., Dynia, J. M., & Lai, M. H. (2021). Early childhood Special education teachers' self-efficacy in relation to individual children: Links to children's literacy learning. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 54, 153-163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2020.09.002>
- Guo, Y., Justice, L. M., Kaderavek, J. N., & McGinty, A. (2012). The literacy environment of preschool classrooms: Contributions to children's emergent literacy growth. *Journal of research in reading*, 35(3), 308-327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9817.2010.01467.x>
- Grynszpan, O., Weiss, P. L., Perez-Diaz, F., & Gal, E. (2014). Innovative technology-based interventions for autism spectrum disorders: a meta-analysis. *Autism*, 18(4), 346-361. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1362361313476767>
- Harris, J. & Ó Duibhir, P. (2011). *Effective language teaching: A Synthesis of Research*. National Council for Curriculum and Assessment. https://ppli.ie/images/Effective_language_teaching_a_synthesis_of_research.pdf Accessed 30 August 2021
- Hedemark, Å., & Lindberg, J. (2018). Babies, Bodies, and Books—Librarians' Work for Early Literacy. *Library Trends*, 66(4), 422-441.
- Hill, D. R. (2016). Phonics Based Reading Interventions for Students with Intellectual Disability: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 4(5), 205-214.
- Hindman, A. H., Skibbe, L. E., & Foster, T. D. (2014). Exploring the variety of parental talk during shared book reading and its contributions to preschool language and literacy: Evidence from the Early Childhood Longitudinal Study-Birth Cohort. *Reading and Writing*, 27(2), 287-313. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-013-9445-4>
- Hirsh-Pasek, K., Golinkoff, R. M., Berk, L. E., & Singer, D. (2009). *A mandate for playful learning in preschool: Applying the scientific evidence*. New York: Oxford University Press
- Hudson, M. E., & Test, D. W. (2011). Evaluating the evidence base of shared story reading to promote literacy for students with extensive support needs. *Research and Practice for Persons with Severe Disabilities*, 36(1-2), 34-45. <https://doi.org/10.2511%2Frpds.36.1-2.34>
- Janosky, J. E. (2005). Use of the single subject design for practice based primary care research. *Postgraduate medical journal*, 81(959), 549-551. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/pgmj.2004.031005>
- Joseph, L., Ross, K., Xia, Q., Amspaugh, L. A., & Accurso, J. (2021). Reading Comprehension Instruction for Students with Intellectual Disabilities: A Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2021.1892033>
- *Justice, L. M., Logan, J. A., Kaderavek, J. N., & Dynia, J. M. (2015). Print-focused read-alouds in early childhood special education programs. *Exceptional Children*, 81(3), 292-311. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0014402914563693>
- *Khowaja, K., & Salim, S. S. (2013). A systematic review of strategies and computer-based intervention (CBI) for reading comprehension of children with autism. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 7(9), 1111-1121.

- Khowaja, K., Salim, S. S., Asemi, A., Ghulamani, S., & Shah, A. (2020). A systematic review of modalities in computer-based interventions (CBIs) for language comprehension and decoding skills of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 19(2), 213-243. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-019-00646-1>
- Kiewer, C. (2008). *Seeing all kids as readers: A new vision for literacy in the inclusive early childhood classroom*. Baltimore: Paul H. Brookes
- Knight, V., McKissick, B. R., & Saunders, A. (2013). A review of technology-based interventions to teach academic skills to students with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 43(11), 2628-2648. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-013-1814-y>
- Kratochwill, T. R., Hitchcock, J., Horner, R. H., Levin, J. R., Odom, S. L., Rindskopf, D. M., & Shadish, W. R. (2010). *Single-case designs technical documentation*. What works clearinghouse. http://ies.ed.gov/ncee/wwc/pdf/wwc_scd.pdf Accessed 30 August 2021
- Kuhl, P. K. (2000). A new view of language acquisition. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 97(22), 11850-11857. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.97.22.11850>
- Lämsä, J., Hämäläinen, R., Aro, M., Koskimaa, R., & Äyrämö, S. M. (2018). Games for enhancing basic reading and maths skills: A systematic review of educational game design in supporting learning by people with learning disabilities. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(4), 596-607. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12639>
- Lee, J., & Yoon, S. Y. (2017). The effects of repeated reading on reading fluency for students with reading disabilities: A meta-analysis. *Journal of learning disabilities*, 50(2), 213-224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2F0022219415605194>
- Leech, K., McNally, S., Daly, M., & Corriveau, K. (2022). Unique effects of book-reading at 9-months on vocabulary development at 36-months: Insights from a nationally representative sample of Irish families. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 58, p.242-253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2021.09.009>
- Lewis, B., & Norwich, A. (2005). *Special teaching for special children? Pedagogies for inclusion*. Berkshire, England: Open University Press
- Lillard, A. S., Lerner, M. D., Hopkins, E. J., Dore, R. A., Smith, E. D., & Palmquist, C. M. (2013). The impact of pretend play on children's development: a review of the evidence. *Psychological bulletin*, 139(1), 1. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0029321>
- Lindner, K. T., & Schwab, S. (2020). Differentiation and individualisation in inclusive education: a systematic review and narrative synthesis. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2020.1813450>
- Lingo, A. S., Barton-Arwood, S. M., & Jolivette, K. (2011). Teachers working together: Improving learning outcomes in the inclusive classroom-practical strategies and examples. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 43(3), 6-13.
- Liu, Y., Fisher, L., Forbes, K., & Evans, M. (2017). The knowledge base of teaching in linguistically diverse contexts: 10 grounded principles of multilingual classroom pedagogy for EAL. *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 17(4), 378-395. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708477.2017.1368136>
- Lorah, E. R., & Parnell, A. (2014). The acquisition of letter writing using a portable multi-media player in young children with developmental disabilities. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 26(6), 655-666. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10882-014-9386-0>

- Losinski, M., Cuenca-Carlino, Y., Zablocki, M., & Teagarden, J. (2014). Examining the efficacy of self-regulated strategy development for students with emotional or behavioral disorders: A meta-analysis. *Behavioral Disorders, 40*(1), 52-67. <https://doi.org/10.17988%2F0198-7429-40.1.52>
- MacGiolla Phádraig, B. (2007). Towards inclusion: The development of provision for children with special educational needs in Ireland from 1991 to 2004. *Irish Educational Studies, 26*(3), 289-300. <https://www.tandfonline.com/action/showCitFormats?doi=10.1080/03323310701491562>
- * Mandak, K., Light, J., & McNaughton, D. (2019). Digital books with dynamic text and speech output: Effects on sight word reading for preschoolers with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders, 49*(3), 1193-1204. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-018-3817-1>
- McNally, S., McCrory, C., Quigley, J., & Murray, A. (2019). Decomposing the social gradient in children's vocabulary skills at 3 years of age: a mediation analysis using data from a large representative cohort study. *Infant Behavior and Development, 57*, 101326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infbeh.2019.04.008>
- Molbaek, M. (2018). Inclusive teaching strategies—dimensions and agendas. *International Journal of Inclusive Education, 22*(10), 1048-1061. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2017.1414578>
- Muhinyi, A., & Rowe, M. L. (2019). Shared reading with preverbal infants and later language development. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 64*, 101053. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2019.101053>
- Nation, K., Clarke, P., Wright, B., & Williams, C. (2006). Patterns of reading ability in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders, 36*(7), 911. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-006-0130-1>
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (2009). *Aistear: The Early Childhood Curriculum Framework*, Dublin 2: The Stationery Office. https://www.ncca.ie/media/2022/aistear_the_early_childhood_curriculum_framework.pdf Accessed 30 August 2021
- National Council for Special Education (2016). *Annual report 2016*. Trim: National Council for Special Education. <http://ncse.ie/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/NCSE-Annual-Report-2016.pdf> Accessed 30 August 2021
- National Council for Special Education (2017). *Annual report 2017*. Trim: National Council for Special Education. <http://ncse.ie/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/NCSE-Annual-Report-2017-English.pdf> Accessed 30 August 2021
- National Educational Psychological Service (2020). *Effective interventions for struggling readers: A good practice guide for teachers*. Department of Education and Skills: https://www.education.ie/en/education-staff/information/neps-literacy-resource/neps_literacy_good_practice_guide.pdf Accessed 30 August 2021
- National Reading Panel (US), National Institute of Child Health, & Human Development (US). (2000). *Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction*: National Institute of Child Health and Human Development, National Institutes of Health.
- Oxley, E., & De Cat, C. (2021). A systematic review of language and literacy interventions in children and adolescents with English as an additional language (EAL). *The Language Learning Journal, 49*(3), 265-287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2019.1597146>

- * Pears, K. C., Kim, H. K., Fisher, P. A., & Yoerger, K. (2016). Increasing pre-kindergarten early literacy skills in children with developmental disabilities and delays. *Journal of School Psychology, 57*, 15-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2016.05.004>
- Pennington, R. C. (2010). Computer-assisted instruction for teaching academic skills to students with autism spectrum disorders: A review of literature. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities, 25*(4), 239-248. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1088357610378291>
- Pennington, R. C., & Delano, M. E. (2012). Writing instruction for students with autism spectrum disorders: A review of literature. *Focus on autism and other developmental disabilities, 27*(3), 158-167. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1088357612451318>
- Peters, J. L., De Losa, L., Bavin, E. L., & Crewther, S. G. (2019). Efficacy of dynamic visuo-attentional interventions for reading in dyslexic and neurotypical children: A systematic review. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews, 100*, 58-76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.02.015>
- Petrovska, I. V., & Trajkovski, V. (2019). Effects of a computer-based intervention on emotion understanding in children with autism spectrum conditions. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders, 49*(10), 4244-4255. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-019-04135-5>
- *Piasta, S. B., Sawyer, B., Justice, L. M., O'Connell, A. A., Jiang, H., Dogucu, M., & Khan, K. S. (2020). Effects of Read It Again! in early childhood special education classrooms as compared to regular shared book reading. *Journal of Early Intervention, 42*(3), 224-243. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1053815119883410>
- * Quinn, E. D., Kaiser, A. P., & Ledford, J. R. (2020). Teaching preschoolers with Down syndrome using augmentative and alternative communication modeling during small group dialogic reading. *American journal of speech-language pathology, 29*(1), 80-100. https://doi.org/10.1044/2019_AJSLP-19-0017
- *Rahn, N. L., Coogle, C. G., & Storie, S. (2016). Preschool children's use of thematic vocabulary during dialogic reading and activity-based intervention. *The Journal of Special Education, 50*(2), 98-108. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022466915622202>
- Ramdoss, S., Lang, R., Mulloy, A., Franco, J., O'Reilly, M., Didden, R., & Lancioni, G. (2011a). Use of computer-based interventions to teach communication skills to children with autism spectrum
- Ramdoss, S., Mulloy, A., Lang, R., O'Reilly, M., Sigafos, J., Lancioni, G., Didden, R., & El Zein, F. (2011b). Use of computer-based interventions to improve literacy skills in students with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review. *Journal of Behavioral Education, 20*(1), 55-76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10864-010-9112-7>
- Ramdoss, S., Machalicek, W., Rispoli, M., Mulloy, A., Lang, R., & O'Reilly, M. (2012). Computer-based interventions to improve social and emotional skills in individuals with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review. *Developmental neurorehabilitation, 15*(2), 119-135. <https://doi.org/10.3109/17518423.2011.651655>
- Rankin, C. (2016). Library services for the early years: Policy, practice, and the politics of the age. *Library Trends, 65*(1), 5-18.
- Reichow, B., Lemons, C. J., Maggin, D. M., & Hill, D. R. (2019). Beginning reading interventions for children and adolescents with intellectual disability. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, (12)*. 10.1002/14651858.CD011359.pub2

- Senokossoff, G. W. (2016). Developing reading comprehension skills in high-functioning children with autism spectrum disorder: A review of the research, 1990–2012. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 32(3), 223-246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10573569.2014.936574>
- Shonkoff, J. P., & Philips, D. A. (2000). *Development. From Neurons to Neighborhoods: The Science of Early Childhood Development Rethinking Nature and Nurture*. Washington: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/9824>
- Singh, B. D., Moore, D. W., Furlonger, B. E., Anderson, A., Fall, R., & Howorth, S. (2021). Reading comprehension and autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review of interventions involving single-case experimental designs. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 8(1), 3-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-020-00200-3>
- Stevens, E. A., Walker, M. A., & Vaughn, S. (2017). The effects of reading fluency interventions on the reading fluency and reading comprehension performance of elementary students with learning disabilities: A synthesis of the research from 2001 to 2014. *Journal of learning disabilities*, 50(5), 576-590. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022219416638028>
- Storch, S. A., & Whitehurst, G. J. (2002). Oral language and code-related precursors to reading: evidence from a longitudinal structural model. *Developmental psychology*, 38(6), 934. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0012-1649.38.6.934>
- Toews, S. G., & Kurth, J. A. (2019). Literacy instruction in general education settings: A call to action. *Research and Practice for Persons with Severe Disabilities*, 44(3), 135-142. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1540796919855373>
- *Towson, J. A., Gallagher, P. A., & Bingham, G. E. (2016). Dialogic reading: Language and preliteracy outcomes for young children with disabilities. *Journal of Early Intervention*, 38(4), 230-246. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1053815116668643>
- *Travers, J. C., Higgins, K., Pierce, T., Boone, R., Miller, S., & Tandy, R. (2011). Emergent literacy skills of preschool students with autism: A comparison of teacher-led and computer-assisted instruction. *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 326-338. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23880589>
- Tupou, J., van der Meer, L., Waddington, H., & Sigafos, J. (2019). Preschool interventions for children with autism spectrum disorder: A review of effectiveness studies. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-019-00170-1>
- Verma, P., & Lahiri, U. (2021). Deficits in Handwriting of Individuals with Autism: a Review on Identification and Intervention Approaches. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-020-00234-7>
- Verschuur, R., Didden, R., Lang, R., Sigafos, J., & Huskens, B. (2014). Pivotal repositone treatment for children with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 1 (1), 34-61. <https://doi.org/10/1007/s40489-013-0008-z>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1962). Thought and Word. In L. Vygotsky & E. Hanfmann, G. Vakar (Eds.), *Thought and language* (pp. 119–153). MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.1037/11193-007>
- *Wanzek, J., Stevens, E. A., Williams, K. J., Scammacca, N., Vaughn, S., & Sargent, K. (2018). Current evidence on the effects of intensive early reading interventions. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 51(6), 612-624. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022219418775110>

- Wasik, B. A., & Bond, M. A. (2001). Beyond the pages of a book: Interactive book reading and language development in preschool classrooms. *Journal of educational psychology*, 93(2), 243. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-0663.93.2.243>
- Weisberg, D. S., Hirsh-Pasek, K., & Golinkoff, R. M. (2013). Guided play: Where curricular goals meet a playful pedagogy. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 7(2), 104-112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mbe.12015>
- Westerveld, M. F., Trembath, D., Shellshear, L., & Paynter, J. (2016). A systematic review of the literature on emergent literacy skills of preschool children with autism spectrum disorder. *The Journal of Special Education*, 50(1), 37-48. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022466915613593>
- Whitehurst, G. J., & Lonigan, C. J. (1998). Child development and emergent literacy. *Child development*, 69(3), 848-872. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.1998.tb06247.x>
- * Wilcox, M. J., Gray, S. I., Guimond, A. B., & Lafferty, A. E. (2011). Efficacy of the TELL language and literacy curriculum for preschoolers with developmental speech and/or language impairment. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 26(3), 278-294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2010.12.003>
- Williams, D., Botting, N., & Boucher, J. (2008). Language in autism and specific language impairment: Where are the links?. *Psychological bulletin*, 134(6), 944. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0013743>
- Williams, J., Murray, A., McCrory, C., & McNally, S. (2013). *Growing Up in Ireland national longitudinal study of children: development from birth to three years infant cohort*. Dublin: Department of Children and Youth Affairs. <http://hdl.handle.net/10147/555696> Accessed 30 August 2021
- Williams, K. J., Walker, M. A., Vaughn, S., & Wanzek, J. (2017). A synthesis of reading and spelling interventions and their effects on spelling outcomes for students with learning disabilities. *Journal of learning disabilities*, 50(3), 286-297. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022219415619753>
- Zucker, T. A., Cabell, S. Q., Justice, L. M., Pentimonti, J. M., & Kaderavek, J. N. (2013). The role of frequent, interactive prekindergarten shared reading in the longitudinal development of language and literacy skills. *Developmental psychology*, 49(8), 1425.

Short biographical notes

Dr Sinéad McNally is a developmental psychologist at the DCU Institute of Education. Her published research investigates children's early language and learning through play and reading, including a special focus on the development of young autistic children in educational contexts. Sinéad is lead Principal Investigator of an interdisciplinary study on the educational experiences of autistic pupils in primary and secondary schools in Ireland. Funded by a COALESCE award from the Irish Research Council, this is the first large-scale systematic study on the experiences of autistic pupils in Ireland. For her research on children's early language and literacy development, Sinéad has been awarded faculty fellowships at Boston University and at the DCU Institute of Education, and funding awards from Science Foundation Ireland, the Standing Conference on Teacher Education North and South, and the European Consortium of Innovative Universities. She teaches research methods and child development to pre-service early childhood educators and leads a team of early career researchers at the School of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education.

Ms Christina O’Keeffe

Christina O’Keeffe is an Assistant Professor at the School of Inclusive and Special Education at the DCU Institute of Education. Christina holds a Bachelor of Education and Psychology and Graduate Diploma in Special Education Needs from Mary Immaculate College (MIC). The majority of her teaching career has focused on supporting autistic children within early childhood education. Christina is currently undertaking a research PhD scholarship, funded by Dublin City University’s Educational Trust, based on the role of play for inclusion within early childhood education. Her published research on the role of play in Early Childhood Education for the inclusion of young autistic children highlights the importance of play in special education.

Table 1. List and key features of systematic reviews on literacy supports for children with additional needs in Education (broad range of ages)

Reference	Sample Age Range	Disabilities	Literacy Instructional Approach	Literacy Outcomes
Afacan et al. (2018)	7.5-9.4 (MA)	Intellectual Disability	Multicomponent Reading Interventions	Reading Skills
Alnahdi (2015)	6-72 years	Intellectual Disability	Any Instructional Strategy that targeted reading skills	Any reading skills
Alquraini & Rao (2020)	6-15 years	Intellectual Disability, Multiple Disabilities, Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities	Effective Reading Interventions	Reading Skills
Bailey & Arciuli (2020)	3-15 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Instruction focused on any of the following skills: phonemic awareness, phonics, vocabulary, reading fluency, or reading comprehension strategies	Reading outcomes (phonics, reading accuracy, reading fluency, or reading comprehension)
Datchuk et al. (2020)	7-18 years	Learning Disability; EBD; ASD; high-incidence disabilities (8%), Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder; intellectual disability (1%). A total of four students were ELLs (4%).	Any instructional strategy targeting writing skills	Text writing sequences
Datchuk & Kubina (2013)	6-10 years (MA)	Learning Disability	Any instructional strategy targeting sentence level skills	Sentence-level skills of handwriting, sentence construction, and grammar/usage
Dessementet et al. (2019)	5-14 years	Intellectual Disability	Phonics Instruction	Decoding Skills
El Zein et al. (2014)	7-17 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Reading Comprehension Interventions	Reading Comprehension
Finnegan & Mazin (2010)	7-17 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Any instructional strategy targeting reading comprehension	Reading Comprehension
Gillespie & Graham (2014)	NS (Grade 1-12)	Learning Disabilities	Writing Interventions	Writing Quality
Hill (2016)	6-21 years	Intellectual Disability	Phonics-based Reading Interventions	Reading Outcomes
Hudson & Test (2011)	3-14 years	Intellectual Disability, ASD or Multiple Disabilities	Shared Story Reading	Any Literacy Skills
Joseph et al. (2021)	6-72 years	Intellectual Disability	Any Instructional Strategy that targeted comprehension skills beyond vocabulary	Reading comprehension
Khowaja et al. (2020)	3-16 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Computer-based Interventions	Language Comprehension and Decoding Skills

Knight (2013)	3-18 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Technology-based interventions	Academic Skills (Including Literacy related skills)
Lamsa et al. (2018)	4-12 years	Learning Disabilities	Educational Games	Reading Skills
Lee & Yuon (2017)	NS (Grade 1-11)	Reading Disabilities	Repeated Reading	Reading Fluency
Losinski et al. (2014)	7.53-16.3 (Mean Age Range)	Emotional or Behavioural Disorders	Self-Regulated Strategy Instruction	Writing Skills
Pennington & Delano (2012)	4-21 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Writing Instruction	Writing Skills
Peters et al. (2019)	5-15 years	Dyslexia	Computerised Dynamic Visuo-Attentional Interventions	Dynamic visuo-attentional processes e.g. visuo-attention/processing/perception
Ramdoss et al. (2011a)	3-14 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Computer-based interventions	Communication skills (expressive language (e.g., vocal imitation, response to questions, commenting, making requests, or greetings) or receptive language (e.g., identification of target vocabulary words)
Ramdoss et al. (2011b)	3-21 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Computer-based interventions	Literacy skills (reading, writing, vocabulary)
Reichow et al. (2019)	4-21 years	Intellectual Disability	Reading Interventions	Beginning reading skills
Singh et al. (2021)	6-17 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Reading comprehension interventions	Text-Based Reading Comprehension
Senokossoff (2016)	3-26 years	High Functioning ASD	Reading comprehension instruction	Reading Comprehension
Stevens et al. (2017)	7-11 years	Learning Disabilities	Reading Fluency Interventions	Reading Fluency and Comprehension
Verma & Lahiri (2021)	4-14 years	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Handwriting interventions (Conventional; Computer-assisted and Robot-Assisted techniques)	Handwriting Skills (Spatial, Temporal and Kinaesthetic Aspects)
Williams et al. (2017)	7-18 years	Learning Disabilities	Reading and Spelling Interventions	Spelling Outcomes

Table 2. Data extraction from a systematic review of systematic reviews on literacy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education

Author, Year, Country	Sample Characteristics			Name/Instructional /Intervention Focus	Number of Studies Included	Literacy Skills Targeted	Effect Size (If Available)	Findings
	Number of Participants (i.e. total number of participants included across studies)	Age Range; % of Population in Early years (0-7)	SEN/Disability					
Boyle et al. (2019) USA	39	2-14 years; 55%	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Shared Reading	11	Key early language and literacy skills described as: listening comprehension, expressive communication, participation (non-communicative), or combination (i.e., reported behaviours are a mixture of participation, listening comprehension, and expressive communication	Overall effect size for shared reading was moderate (.51-.70) however, specific features of the 11 studies were associated with stronger effects on some outcomes	<p>The impact of shared reading was most clearly observed on outcome measures of listening comprehension, participation (non-communicative), and combination outcomes that included communicative and non-communicative acts; small effect sizes were observed for measures of expressive communication.</p> <p>Positive effects occurred with children of ages 2 to 14, and with parents, teachers, and researchers as reading partners. Effect sizes ranging from small to very large were observed with a variety of intervention partners, for a mixture of intervention packages, and with multiple outcome measures.</p> <p>Interventions that evaluated listening comprehension yielded a large level of effect; interventions that investigated expressive communication reported a small level of effect size. Interventions targeting participation (non-communicative) yielded a moderate level of effect. Interventions examining</p>

changes in child behaviours that were a combination of communicative and non-communicative acts reported a very large level of effect.

Khowaja & Salim (2013) Malaysia	189	20 months-16 years; 63%	Autism Spectrum Disorder	1)Strategies of Vocabulary Instruction and Text Comprehension Instruction 2) Computer-based Interventions using these above methods	8	Reading Comprehension	N/A	Results indicate that 2 strategies of vocabulary instruction appear to be more commonly used: Multimedia methods and explicit instruction Regarding text comprehension instruction, the strategy of Question Answering appears to be more commonly used CBI for reading comprehension was used across 5/11 studies and results reveal positive learning outcome using this approach
Wanzek et al. (2018) USA	3, 646	NS (Kindergarten-Grade 3); 88%	Students with learning disabilities and at risk of reading difficulties (Low ability; low phonemic awareness; language disorders)	Intensive Early Reading Interventions (classified as 100 sessions or longer)	25	Early Literacy Outcomes in an Alphabetic Language	The weighted mean effect size (ES) estimate (ES = 0.39), with a mean effect size adjusted for publication bias (ES = 0.28), both significantly different from zero, suggested intensive early reading interventions resulted in positive outcomes for early struggling readers in kindergarten through third grades	Results of this meta-analysis indicate that intensive interventions result in positive gains in reading performance for struggling readers in Grades K through 3. Attempted to identify features of the interventions that were associated with increased effectiveness; however, we did not find significant heterogeneity in effect sizes across studies There is limited variability in the effects, indicating that intervention commonalities may be driving the positive effects more than differences such as group size or duration. Intervention commonalities across studies included the following: (a) a high level of standardization (b) instructional

content addressing phonological awareness, phonics and word recognition and fluency and (c) school staff or community members implemented the interventions.

Table 3. Data extraction from a systematic review of the literature on literacy supports for children with additional needs in Early Childhood Education

Author, Year, Country	Sample Characteristics											
	Number	Age (as reported by authors in years and/or months)	Gender	Professional Diagnosis	Methodology	Name	Intervention Components	Frequency, Intensity, Duration	Interventionist	Setting /Context	Target Literacy Outcomes	Results
Benedek-Wood et al. (2016) USA	3 children with ASD	3.6-5.6 years; M=4.43 years	3 Male	Autism Spectrum Disorder and limited speech	Single-subject Multiple-probe across participants	Letter-Sound Correspondence Instruction	Six lower-case letters identified as unknown to participants were selected for the intervention (o, t, r, l, u, p). Intervention sessions consisted of approx. 15 minutes of instructional activities (10 minute-instruction; 5 minute-extension activity) and optional 5-minute choice activities if time permitted to reinforce participants' engagement during the sessions.	Five times weekly; 20 minutes; 2 months	Researcher	Preschool; ASD Special Class (N=2); NS	Acquisition of Letter-Sound Correspondence: Frequency of correct performance on probe whereby researcher presented a letter sound orally and participants were required to select the target letter from a field of six letter choices targeted during the intervention (o, t, r, l, u, p). Responses were considered correct only if the first attempt was made within 5s	Positive: All three participants demonstrated an increase in total number of correct responses provided during LSC probe after instruction
Botts et al. (2014) USA	5 children with disabilities	4.2-5.7 years; M= 4.74 years	5 Males	Mild-Moderate Language Impairment	Modified Alternating Treatments Design	Activity-based Intervention V Embedded Direct Instruction	Activity-based intervention and embedded direct instruction were compared using four features: nature of transaction (routine or planned activities of interest V ongoing activity); introduction of goals (embedded within meaningful routine, planned and child-initiated activities V embedded within variety of ongoing activities); antecedents and consequences (logical occurring antecedents meaningfully related to child's response V scripted and identical antecedents); generalisation (different types of antecedents resulting in generalisation cross events, objectives and settings	Twice weekly activity-based and embedded direct instruction sessions; 20 minute sessions; 6 weeks	Trained Certified Speech and Language Therapist (n=2)	University based inclusive preschool language classroom; Circle time, reading time or craft time	Age-appropriate emergent literacy skills unfamiliar to the participants: Activity-Based Intervention treatment objectives: Phonological Skills: 1) Producing alliteration; 2) Blending two-syllable words; 3) Producing rhyming	Positive in favour of embedded direct instruction: this approach resulted in more effective and efficient acquisition of phonological awareness than the use of activity-based intervention; and more children reached criterion for target objectives with a faster rate of acquisition and a lower percentage of errors for objectives taught

							V constant scripted antecedents until response learned)				Embedded-Direct Instruction treatment objectives: 1) Blending words presented in onset and rime; 2) Identifying alliteration; 3) Segmenting compound words	
Boyle et al. (2021) USA	6 dyads (child with disability and typically developing peer)	3.10-5.4 years M=4.35 years	2 Male; 4 Female	Developmental disability	Single-subject Multiple-probe design across participants	Shared e-Book Reading with Dynamic Text and Speech Output	At the beginning of each intervention session, the researcher first asked one of the two children to choose a book on the tablet, alternating between the children in the dyad. For each page (and associated target word), the researcher then read the text at the bottom of the page, and the first child activated the hot spot of the target word, implementing a least-to-most prompting hierarchy (spoken prompt; additional spoken and visual prompt; spoken cue; hand-over-hand) if required. Researchers provided expansions of descriptive words, as well as child comments and praise for on-task behaviour if required.	Average twice weekly (range 1-3); approx. 5 minutes (ranged 4-6 minutes); 13 weeks	Researcher	2 Inclusive preschool classrooms; daily classroom activities (play)	Single-Word Reading Skills; Examination of number of words (from 10 target words) identified correctly by participant with a disability during probe sessions.	Positive: All six participants with disabilities demonstrated an increase in the total number of correct responses during the single-word reading probes.
Colozzo et al. (2016) Canada	15 children with DS	3.3-6.10 years; M=4.11 years	10 Male; 5 Female	Down Syndrome. Additional diagnosis of ASD (N=3), apraxia (n=1) and one child was EAL	Pre-test Post-test Design	Early Reading Program: Hybrid approach to reading instruction combining whole word (visual) and analytic (phonic/sound based) reading strategies	Student chose personal book to read aloud for teacher; teacher then selected book for shared reading session with student. After book reading activities, engaged in sight word practice and play including letter naming/sound practice and phonological awareness tasks for approx. 30 minutes. Each sessions generally concluded with another shared book reading before final 5-10 minute discussion with parent or special education assistant	Weekly Sessions; duration; 45 weeks	Researcher Parents and/or school special education assistants also commitment at least 20 minutes practice sessions 4 times weekly	Research Centre; NS	Early Literacy and Phonological Awareness; Letter Identification: Sound Identification; Concepts of Print; Sight Words Language: Receptive Language; Peabody Picture Test 4th Ed.; Expressive Language Skills; Mean Length of Utterance and Length of Longest Utterance assessed as part of Video recorded language sample of child play; Level of Expressive Language was also coded according to language sample	Mixed: All students improved on all literacy measures post-intervention (Phonological awareness; letter identification, sound identification, concepts of print, sight words) All but one student increased MLU and MLLU AI but two students progressed to a higher expressive language level or remained in the highest level over the course of the program
Guo et al. (2021) USA	73 early childhood special educators; 837 children (303 with disability)	2.92-5.83 years; M=4.3 years	463 Male; 374 Female	Speech or Language Impairment (N=101); ASD (n=33);	Survey Design	Teacher Self-Efficacy	Online survey examined whether teachers experience differences in self-efficacy when teaching children with disabilities in comparison to typically developing children and whether they experience differences in self-efficacy when teaching children with different types of disabilities; Examined whether there are direct relations between child-specific teacher self-efficacy and children's print knowledge outcomes; Examine whether and to what extent children's disability status moderates the relations between child-specific teacher self-efficacy and children's print knowledge outcomes	N/A	Early Childhood Special Education Teachers	Public Schools (n=74); Majority inclusion classrooms (n=NS); children with disabilities and typically	Print Knowledge measured using Phonological Awareness Literacy Screening Pre-K. Subtests based on; 1) letter identification; 2) print and word awareness; 3) name writing Child-Specific Teacher Self-Efficacy: Teacher self-efficacy was measured using the child-specific teacher self-efficacy scale	Early Childhood Special Education teachers felt less self-efficacious with children with disabilities versus typically developing children Teachers experienced the lowest efficacy for teaching children with ASD among children with disabilities Teachers' self-efficacy in relation to individual children was a significant predictor of children's print knowledge (letter identification, print and word awareness and

developing peers); NS

name writing) for all children including those with disabilities and typically developing peers

Justice et al. (2015) USA	291 children with disabilities	NR; M=52 months	61 Male; 230 Female	Language Impairment (Either as primary or secondary diagnosis); Sample included children with ASD (n=31); cerebral palsy (n=6); Down Syndrome (n=4); ADHD (n=2)	Quasi-experimental with Random Assignment to Conditions	Print-Focused Read-Alouds	Classrooms were randomly assigned to one of three conditions: regular reading (teacher?)/regular reading (caregiver?) (n=28); print focused/regular reading (n=27); print focused/print focused (n=29). Teachers and caregivers were provided with set of 30 storybooks and were instructed to read according to specified approach i.e. regular reading involving normal reading style or print-focused reading style whereby teachers read each storybook and naturally embedded discussion about specified specific print-reference targets regarding book and print organisation, print meaning, letters and words. For each storybook, a two-page insert was included that provided examples of how to engage children in print-focused discussions specific to the objectives aligned to that book	Four-times weekly; 30 weeks; duration NS; total 120 sessions over academic year	Trained Early Childhood Special Education Teachers (n=83)	Early Childhood Special Classrooms (including both typically developing peers and children with disabilities); Home environment	Print Knowledge: Based on composite index of three constructs: 1) Print concept knowledge (preschool word and print awareness); 2) Alphabet knowledge (Subtests of Phonological Awareness and Literacy Screening Pre-K); 3) Name writing (Name Writing Subtest of PALS Pre-K)	Positive in favour of teachers who used print-focused read-alouds: children scored significantly better in print knowledge (Print concept knowledge; alphabet knowledge; name writing) than those whose teachers engaged in typical reading practice Children whose teachers and caregivers implemented print-focused read-alouds simultaneously demonstrated modestly higher differences however these were not significant
Lorah & Parnell (2014) USA	3	4.6-6 years M=5.2 years	2 Male; 1 Female	Developmental Delay/disability	Multiple baseline design	Use of iPod Touch, stylus pen and application 'Letter School'	During training, the participant completed the three-phased letter training protocol: The first phase involved tapping or touching the starting point for each of the letters lines; the second phase involved tracing the letter; and the third phase involved writing the letter without a model. All three phases were completed using the stylus pen. Once the participant completed all three steps they were then presented with a piece of paper, with the target letter written proportionately on the top of the paper and a standard pencil instructed to "write (insert letter).	NR	NR	Education Centre; Unused OT office	Letter Writing Acquisition: Task analysis and probe: For each letter, a percentage of steps completed correctly was calculated Participant preference in terms of instruction begin conducted on the iPod Touch® with the application Letter School or on a paper with a pencil.	Mixed; results indicate that for two of the three participants successfully acquired handwriting skills using the instructional procedures contained within the application. Participant preference indicated that two of the three children preferred iPod Touch® with the application Letter School over a paper with a pencil with one participant demonstrating preference for paper and pencil task
Mandek et al. (2019) USA	3 children with ASD	3.7-4.7 years; M=4.2 years	3 Male	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Single-subject Multiple-probe across participants design	Dynamic Text and Speech Output Tablet Software	10 written target words were presented on an app, EasyVSD1 on a tablet device. Individual pages of the book ("Brown Bear Brown Bear What do you See?") were displayed with one of the words displayed upon selection of the hotspot of the animal. After each individual page was read, the researcher paused and provided the opportunity for the child to active the hot spot. Each page had one hot spot which, when activated, either displayed speech alone or text and speech. Individual pages which contained target words featured both text and speech while pages without target words featured only speech.	Twice weekly; 10-15 minutes;	Researcher	Early Intervention Inclusive Preschool (LEAP) (children ASD and typically developing peers); secluded area of classroom or school building	Percentage of sight words read correctly: Participants' accuracy in identifying 10 target sight words.	Positive: Moderate to large effects were reported across all three participants

Pears et al. (2016) USA	209 children (112 intervention group; 113 comparison group)	NS M=5.26 years	86 Male; 26 Female Just intervention group, report on all?	Developmental Disability or delay & additional behavioural, social or attentional difficulties	Randomised Control Trial	Kids in Transition to School (KITS) Program; The KITS Program is a short-term, intensive school readiness intervention designed to fill the summer services gap and augment the school readiness skills of children at high risk for difficulties with academic and social adjustment to school.	The curricular objectives were clearly specified for each session by skill domain (Early Literacy; Self-Regulatory; pro-social skills). Skills were introduced at circle time lessons. The daily activities (e.g., art projects, dramatic activities) were designed to practice the session skills. Early literacy activities included a letter of the day, a poem of the week, and storybook and dramatic activities.	Twice weekly; 2-hours; 24 sessions (School readiness phase 2-months prior kindergarten entry)	Researchers (Lead teacher + 2 assistant teachers) Parent/Caregiver involvement	Centre or school-based classrooms; School readiness groups; Home environment	Pre-Kindergarten literacy skills: Letter naming and phonemic awareness measured using the Letter Naming Fluency (LNF) and Initial Sound Fluency (ISF) subtests of the Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills; Understanding of concepts about print measured using the 24-item Concepts About Print Test	Positive; Results showed that the intervention had a significant small positive effect on children's literacy skills from baseline to the end of summer before the start of kindergarten (d = .14). The intervention also had significant indirect effects on teacher ratings of children's literacy skills during the fall of their kindergarten year (β = .09) Additionally, when scores were compared to standard benchmarks, a greater percentage of the children who received the intervention moved from being at risk for reading difficulties to having low risk.
Piasta et al. (2020) USA	726 (341 with disabilities; 385 peers) 374 children	NR M=52.4 months	428 Male; 298 Female (n=95); autism spectrum disorder (n=31); emotional	Speech or language impairment (n=95); developmental delay (n=55); autism spectrum disorder (n=31); emotional	Randomised Waitlist Control Trial	Read It Again	Classrooms randomised to Read It Again intervention whereby trained teachers implemented supplementary language and literacy intervention, alongside, classroom curriculum within context of whole-class shared book reading based on 15 commercially available books versus comparison group whereby untrained teachers engaged in shared book reading as normal (not using RIA) with identical 15 books. Teachers in the intervention group followed flexible	2-times weekly; 20 minute; 30 weeks, total 60 sessions	Trained Early Childhood Teachers (N=55)-excluding those comparison condition	Public school (n=78) or Head Start (n=31) Schools; Early Childhood Special	Print Knowledge; Preschool Word and Print Awareness Assessment Letter Knowledge; Uppercase and Lowercase Letter Recognition subtests of the Phonological Awareness Literacy Screening for Preschool	Negative No statistically significant or practically meaningful direct effects of intervention on measures of print awareness, letter knowledge, and phonological awareness for children with disabilities or their typically developing peers

	interventi on group			disturbance (n=3); specific learning disability (n=3); intellectual disability (n=2); visual, hearing, orthopaedic, or other health impairment (n=14); or multiple disabilities (n=75); remainder (n=63) not reported/unknown			script and differentiated instruction through scaffolding and use of learner's ladder in order to support children to achieve lesson objectives. Caregivers also received 4 books used as part of intervention, one every 6 weeks, and were encouraged to read to children one per week		Caregivers of children in RIA condition also received four of the books used in RIA, and receiving one book every 6 weeks, and were encouraged to read these to their child once a week	Classrooms (3-5 years); self- contained classrooms (n=29) and inclusive classrooms (n=80)	Phonological Awareness; Rhyme Awareness subtest of the Pre- Reading Inventory of Phonological Awareness Narrative Skills: Renfrew Bus Story Vocabulary Skills; Definitional Vocabulary subtest of the Test of Preschool Early Literacy	No effects on meaning-based skills (narrative and vocabulary) for children with disabilities or their typically developing peers; RIA increased teachers' print knowledge, phonological awareness, narrative, and vocabulary instruction during shared book reading; Teachers' instruction did not predict children's outcomes. However, a small indirect effect was reported on a composite of children's code- based skills, in which RIA meaning-focused instruction affected code-based skills
Quinn et al. (2020) USA	9 (4 children with DS and 5 typically developin g peers)	3.1-5.3 years; M=4.48 years	3 Male;1 Female	Down Syndrome & Severe Speech Sound Disorder	Multiple- probe across behaviours design	Aided Augmentative and Alternative Communicatio n Modelling (AAC-MOD) during Small Group Dialogic Reading	Children were assigned to dyads (Participant with DS and typically developing peer). Picture books were six pages in length and each page contained one target vocabulary word (individualised for each participant). Sessions involved use of RAAP strategy: 1) creating and introduction script to specify task directions for each participant; 2) adding an attending cue; 3) providing verbal reinforcement & AAC-MOD which included an additional three components: Modelling target vocabulary, AAC expansions and recast, addition of AAC input during RAAP steps. This included: 1) read a page containing a target vocabulary word while modelling the target word on the tablet; 2) Praise and ask a question; 3) Pause and wait for response; 4) Prompt child while modelling target word on the tablet; 4) Expand or recast the child's responses	NS; Average Session Duration; 7.32 minutes, total 12 sessions	Researcher (certified SLT)	Inclusive Early Childhood Programs; Child sized tables within or adjacent to classroom	Percentage of Correctly Identified Symbols assessed during vocabulary probe (total of six words); Rate of Symbolic Communication Acts assessed during dialogic reading and thematic play (generalisation); Lexical Diversity (Number of different words used during dialogic reading); Semantic/Syntactic Skills; Number of Multiple words used during dialogic reading	Mixed: all 4 participants increased percentage of correctly identified symbols during the intervention. 3 participants increased rate of symbolic communication acts during dialogic reading with unclear effects for one participant. 2 of 4 participants (with lower expressive vocabulary) increased number of different words used during dialogic reading Inconsistent results reported regarding number of multiple words used during dialogic reading
Rahn et al. (2016) USA	3 children with disabilitie s	3-4 years; M=4 years	1 Male; 2 Female	Communication Delay (n=1); Communication Delay & ADHD (n=1); Cleft Palette (n=1)	Adapted Alternating Treatments Design	Dialogic Reading V Activity-Based Intervention	During DR, the reader focuses on pictures within the book and asks completion, recall, open-ended, wh and distancing questions. The researcher introduced the title and author of the book and asked a question to stimulate interest in the book. The researcher read the entire book in the first session and a shorted version in subsequent sessions. A total of five questions were administered, one per vocabulary items assigned to the DR condition. During ABI, the teacher provides embedded learning opportunities during routines, teacher-led activities and child-initiated activities. When the child showed interest in a target object, the researcher administered a question. The researcher implemented one of the following expansions based on those that were natural within the context of play	Twice daily; 5 times weekly; 2 weeks	Graduate Assistant	2 Pre- kindergarte n Classrooms ; Hallway or teacher's lounge	Rate of Expressive Vocabulary Use: Number of times participants used targeted thematic vocabulary per minute	Mixed: Two participants showed similar rates of use of target vocabulary and small effect sizes in both intervention conditions. For one participant, effect sizes larger for DR V ABI

(expansion, model, definition, prompted imitation, directions, mand, question).												
Towson et al. (2016) USA	42 children with disabilities (21 intervention; 21 comparison group)	NS M=53.57 months	17 Male; 4 Female	Significant Delay (also refer to as developmental disabilities)	Pre-test Post-test Quasi-Experimental Group Design	Dialogic Reading with the incorporation of pause time	Small groups of three to five children participated in the storybook sessions (total of three different storybooks). Children in the intervention book received dialogic reading intervention with pause time (minimum of 5s) and comparison group received typical storybook reading. Each dialogic reading session involved explicit instruction and prompts using the CROWD strategies (completion; recall; open-ended questions; wh questions; distancing) based on up to 5 prompts for targeted vocabulary words (one per one vocabulary word) as well as a maximum of 5 prompts for general receptive and expressive language skills using the PEER strategy(prompt, evaluate, expand, repeat)	Three-times weekly; 10-15 minutes; 6 weeks	Researcher and assistant	12 preschool classrooms (5 inclusive classrooms; 7 special classrooms); Quiet area of preschool classroom	Receptive Language: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test; Which one doesn't belong subtest of Individual Growth and Development Indicators of Early Literacy (IGDI-EL); Near transfer receptive vocabulary task involving total of 45 words Expressive Language: Expressive one-word picture vocabulary test; Picture naming subtest of IGDI-EL; Near transfer expressive vocabulary task involving total of 45 words Pre-literacy Skills: Get ready to read screening tool including print knowledge, book knowledge, phonological awareness and phonics	Mixed; Intervention group demonstrated significant increase in on near-transfer expressive and receptive vocabulary tests across both targeted and untargeted vocabulary No significant differences across remaining measures of receptive and expressive vocabulary, although positive trends were reported in intervention group No significant difference in pre-literacy skills, although positive trends were reported in intervention group
Travers et al. (2011) USA	17 children with ASD	3-6 years; M=NS	NS	Autism Spectrum Disorder	Adapted Alternating Treatments Design	Traditional Teacher-Led Group Instruction using Alphabet Books V Multi-Media Computer Assisted Instruction in teaching alphabet skills	Teacher-Led Group Instruction using Alphabet Books involved teachers reading to children and eliciting student responses to instructional cues in teacher scripts. Teachers provided opportunities to identify target letter for children (e.g. point to target letter) V Computer Assisted Intervention (CAI) Condition: After competing training, children were required to discriminate between number and letter targets. During mastery lessons they were required to discriminate between current and previous target letters. Short games were also included to motivate children and reinforce learning.	4-times weekly; 10 minute instruction; 4 weeks	Special Education Class Teacher	Elementary schools (n=9); Preschool classrooms for children with ASD; NS	Receptive and Expressive Letter Recognition Skills; The Brigance Diagnostic Inventory of Early Development 2(IED-2) Student Attention and disruptive Behaviours (e.g. tantrums, aggression) based on partial interval recording system of 10-minute video observations	Positive: Students significantly increased their ability to recognise letters upon conclusion of interventions. This was the case across both intervention types. Therefore, CAI was not more effective than TLI for teaching letter recognition skills Both interventions also resulted in a relatively high rate of student attention and low rates of disruptive behaviours with no significant differences between intervention types
Wilcox et al. (2011) USA	118 children with disabilities (80 treatment group; 30 comparison group)	47-64 months ; M=53.58 Months	88 Male; 30 Female	Developmental Speech and/or Language Impairment (either as primary or secondary impairment)	Randomised control trial	Teaching Early Literacy and Language (TELL) Curriculum Package	Teachers/classes were randomly assigned to experimental (TELL) or contrast BAU condition TELL curriculum package includes scope and sequence of instruction, scripted teaching activities, and materials for implementation of oral language and early literacy activities. Daily curriculum components include: 1) ABC Warmup (letter names) followed by a phonological awareness activity; 2) Focus book reading; 3) Focus book sequence (Picture walk, read, read it again, story re-tell); 4) Vocabulary sequence (say the word,	4 times weekly; 150 minutes of daily instruction; Academic school year	Trained Preschool teachers (n=19) (Mainstream and Special Education)	19 Inclusive Preschool Classrooms ; Implemented as part of five required learning blocks including circle time, story time,	Phonological Awareness: Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals-Preschool 2nd edition (CELF-P2); Phonological Awareness: Phonological Awareness Literacy Screening for Preschool (PALS-PreK) Alphabet Knowledge: Upper-case and lower case letters, print name writing as measured in PALS PreK	Mixed; Children in the TELL condition demonstrated higher oral language scores in VOCAB as well as sentence length in BUS; No statistically significant group differences in CELF-P2 language composite scores although a large percentage of children in the TELL condition outperformed peers in the BAU condition;

explain the meaning, give an example, repeat the word); 5) Table tent cards (script on back); 6) Fact cards (expository language, theme related); 7) Social story cards; 8) ABC action cards (letter chants); 9) music and movement; 10) Three meaningful transitions; 11) Writing/dictation; 12) Phonological awareness warm-up (patterns or sounds).

Curriculum also includes list of recommended supportive practices in order to establish a high quality learning context

snack time, integrated writing and teacher-led activities with option of integrating as part of dramatic play, science, math, art or outside play activities

Sentence Length and Complexity: Renfrew Bus Story

Vocabulary Skills: VOCAB (receptive and expressive vocabulary measure)

Higher scores observed among children for code-focused skills in the TELL condition including phonological awareness on the CELF-P2, letter sounds, beginning sound awareness and rhyme awareness subtests of PALS